

AI Impact on Employee Work Performance and Employee Morale in the Philippines - A Literature Review

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Abstract

In this literature review, the author delves into the profound implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on employee work performance and morale within the Philippines. Employing a discerning and qualitative methodology, this review scrutinizes existing studies on the subject matter, meticulously dissecting the global perspective, regional ramifications, and, specifically, the impact felt within the Philippine context. Unveiling a void in research on how AI engenders shifts in productivity and morale within Philippine workplaces, this review spotlights an imperative need for comprehensive and rigorous investigations to unravel the multifaceted implications of AI, both advantageous and challenging.

Corroborating the findings of an array of studies, this review underscores the dichotomy of opinions permeating Philippine industries with regard to AI. While some enterprises eagerly embrace AI as an indispensable tool fostering augmented productivity and heightened efficiency, others harbor reservations about its latent adverse effects on employee morale and job security. Distilling salient insights from a plethora of sources, this literature review underscores the paramount importance for businesses contemplating the integration of AI into their operations to consider the potential ramifications for their employees judiciously. Furthermore, it implores organizations to take proactive measures to assuage any adverse consequences that may emerge from this technological paradigm shift.

The culmination of this literature review proffers itself as an indispensable compendium for policymakers, researchers, and enterprises seeking to harness AI's transformative potential while prudently minimizing the attendant risks. Through its comprehensive appraisal of extant literature, this review serves as a compass, guiding stakeholders towards a harmonious convergence of AI and human potential, illuminating the path towards realizing the full extent of AI's benefits while nurturing a supportive and forward-looking environment for the Philippine workforce.

Keywords: Employee work performance, Morale, Artificial Intelligence

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence's immediate rise to prominence is a game-changer in today's business world. Automation and optimization of operations, an improvement in data analysis and decision-making, and a new appreciation of consumer behavior are just

some of the areas in AI that have been put to use. The people who work for a business are its most valuable asset since they are the backbone of a successful and sustainable enterprise. The direction in which the company develops as a whole depends on its employees' output. Companies in the contemporary era have, therefore, begun investing more in their workers' professional growth. Both workers and businesses rely heavily on this procedure. To increase efficiency, businesses have begun incorporating cutting-edge technologies into training and development programs for their staff. The study of AI falls within the umbrella of computer science. The idea behind it is to simulate human thought processes. This paper provides a literature assessment on the effects of AI on productivity and dedication in the workplace.

Overall, with the rise in the use of AI in many industries and workplaces, many researchers have sought to investigate the impact of AI in workplaces and on the productivity of specific industries, taking a world and various regional views of the subject. Intriguingly, there is a lack of studies that examine how AI affects productivity and morale on the job in the Philippines. While research into the implications of AI on the workplace is expanding worldwide, a deeper understanding of how AI will change the Filipino workforce is lacking. This literature review will mainly focus on reviewing scholarly publications on the impact of AI on employees' work performance and morale in the Philippines. A survey of 109 business leaders and 100 regular workers was done in the Philippines by Microsoft and International Data Corporation Asia/Pacific. While almost all Philippine business leaders acknowledge that AI is critical to their company's competitiveness, just around half have actually implemented AI solutions. By 2025, businesses that have already begun employing AI anticipate having a competitive edge of 1.5 times (Odugbesan et al., 2023). With the increasing adoption of AI globally, it is expected to have an impact on employee performance and morale in the Philippines.

2. World View

The papers to be reviewed under this subject were taken from online search engines such as Google Scholar and PubMed. The selected search engines hold substantial merit due to comprehensive and extensive coverage. Both have academically recognized reputations amongst the academic and research community due to their rigorous quality control to ensure the credibility of information. To achieve the thorough exploration of the existing literature, an initial search was performed using broad keywords, namely "AI," "employee performance," and "morale." This allowed for an extensive overview of available publications. The initial search resulted in a substantial number of articles, totaling 10,014, without restricting the sources based on jurisdiction. To enhance specificity, additional filters were applied throughout the search process using the keywords "artificial intelligence" alongside "employee performance" and "morale." This narrowing of the search assisted in obtaining more focused results, reducing the number of retrieved papers to over 1,000. Further filtering was deemed necessary to isolate papers that *specifically* explored the impact of AI on employee performance and morale. Consequently, another filter was applied, narrowing the search to studies investigating the effects of "artificial intelligence + impact + employee performance and morale." This filter led to a reduction in the number of articles to just over 100. After the rigorous steps, another meticulous selection process was employed

to ensure utmost relevance and precision in this study. Each article was assessed by thoroughly examining the titles, abstracts, and conclusions for direct relevance to the impact of AI on employee performance and morale. Following this rigorous evaluation, 60 papers were identified as directly pertinent to the study, forming the basis for subsequent analysis and discussion.

Automation of processes and the elimination of boring, repetitive physical labor are two ways in which AI has been proven to boost worker productivity. Artificial intelligence (AI) may also aid in data analysis and decision-making, leading to better outcomes due to better analysis and more informed judgment (Hou et al., 2022). On top of that, AI may enhance customer service by illuminating patterns in consumer behavior and preferences, therefore assisting staff in giving better care to clients. Lastly, AI may help workers be more imaginative in their job by providing feedback on ideas and assisting in developing and refining novel approaches.

Two, this analysis will look at how AI has affected employees' dedication to their jobs. There is evidence to indicate that AI may facilitate the development of a cooperative and trusting work environment (Rejeb et al., 2022). In turn, this may boost productivity since workers will be more invested in their jobs if they know their efforts are appreciated, and their input is respected. Artificial intelligence (AI) may also provide workers greater freedom since AI-powered technologies can help them multitask and get more done in less time (Hou et al., 2023) than ever before. Finally, AI has the potential to boost employee engagement by facilitating the delivery of feedback on their work and providing useful insights into employee performance.

In this investigation, we used an interpretative and qualitative methodology. We took a look at how cutting-edge AI may change the face of business administration over the next ten years. Machine learning technologies, rather than just replacing jobs, are thought to improve human decision-making. Expert opinions on the impact of AI on management, however, may be broken down into two camps: revolutionary and evolutionary, depending on how they interpret the available facts. According to the revolutionaries, the unexpected powers of AI technology will have an effect on the duties of managers at all levels. The evolutionary camp, on the other hand, maintains that while AI will have different impacts on managers and even replace certain activities, it will not bring about any unexpected changes in their work (Khokhar et al., 2022). Consequently, AI has the potential for both constructive and destructive uses. It is both impossible and undesirable to put a stop to or slow down technological development (Fossen et al., 2019). However, strong leadership is required to set it on the right course. The effects of technology on worker attitudes, productivity, and stress are the subject of a separate research project. The impact of technology on the relationships between workers is also investigated. The majority of workers in the research are content with their current technological setup and show an openness to adopting new technologies. Research also indicates that technology has no negative impact on employees' personal connections and may even promote communication among colleagues (Hailiang et al., 2023) in the workplace. Manis and Madhavaram (2023) highlighted that changes in one's job, a drop in social standing, and the fear of replacement by artificial intelligence are the three main causes of identity danger in the workplace. The research paradigm used in this work incorporates quantitative

techniques, including measurement and structural analysis. In addition, model differences between groups are computed using up-to-date criteria.

Studies have also been conducted investigating the consequences of AI. For instance, Ulta Wilkins (Khaskhelly et al., 2023) used a qualitative approach to study AI in the workplace, finding that its implementation improves people's learning and development at work, which in turn boosts their motivation. However, this finding runs counter to the idea that non-AI methods are just as crucial for improving people's skills. In another study, Waseem et al. (2022) posed the question, "How does the workplace affect the motivation of employees?" and conducted a thorough literature analysis on the effect of technology in the workplace. Two hundred thousand publications were chosen after a search for those that related to technology and motivation in general (the research used a quantitative approach and followed a four-step technique). From these papers, 1451 abstracts were chosen; from those, 205 useful publications were chosen; the results indicated that technological progress paves the way for motivational workplaces designs, ultimately resulting in a more motivated workforce as a whole. (Khokhar, Hou, et al., 2020) The use of AI in improving workplace satisfaction and productivity has been a hot topic in recent years. The role that AI may play in raising morale and productivity in the workplace has been the subject of a number of studies. Employing the analytic hierarchy approach, we constructed a model to analyze employee psyche and productivity using AI. Both emotional intelligence (EI) and artificial intelligence (AI) have received much coverage in recent years.

Several studies have looked at how these ideas affect productivity, staff retention, and morale in the workplace. Employee retention and productivity were shown to benefit significantly from higher levels of emotional intelligence. (Kshetri, 2021) AI was also discovered to have a strong moderating effect on worker productivity. In their study, Irlbeck and Dunn established that training in emotional intelligence greatly benefited workers, resulting in higher levels of emotional intelligence and a more positive work environment, and that there is a strong correlation between emotional intelligence and both employee loyalty and productivity, according to the data. The research also shows that AI substantially moderates worker productivity (Irlbeck and Dunn, 2020). Developing workers' emotional intelligence should be a top priority for every business that cares about its human capital. Employees' output, level of contentment in their jobs, and dedication to the success of the company as a whole may all benefit from this. Moreover, a pleasant work atmosphere may be maintained via the development of emotional intelligence (Nawaz et al., 2021).

To better understand how employees in the services and banking industries view the role of change leadership in the introduction of AI and its subsequent effects on their performance and motivation at work, Wijayati et al. (2022) conducted an investigation. This investigation is an example of quantitative research, with data analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM) with the use of the computer programme AMOS 22.0. Only 254 of the 357 participants met the criteria for inclusion in the analysis. Employees of service and financial organizations in East Java, Indonesia, are the focus of this survey (Wijayati et al., 2022). The findings indicate that AI has a very favorable impact on productivity and satisfaction in the workplace (Wijayati et al., 2022). AI's negative effects on performance and engagement in the workplace are mitigated through effective change management. Organizational success is directly tied to the efforts of its employees, making employee performance a critical factor.

AI improves efficiency in the workplace by collecting, processing, and making better use of data (relating to healthcare activities and operations). In addition, AI may be used by management to assess and compare the performance of important competent personnel and workers (Zhou et al., 2021). Artificial intelligence makes it simpler to keep track of a wide variety of medical data, which in turn makes it easier for healthcare providers and their personnel to carry out their duties and increase productivity (Kreutzer and Sirrenberg, 2020). AI not only aids in the precise assessment of worker performance, but it also lays out a plan for self-learning skills and suggests adjustments that might boost output (Tong et al., 2021). Using AI, businesses may connect employees' efforts to organizational objectives (Zhao, Cooke, and Wang 2021). This, in turn, motivates workers to raise output.

Employee productivity may be increased with the aid of AI, which is great for teams. Regular meetings may benefit from the use of these technologies because of the insights they provide. Taking careful notes at meetings may be challenging, but with the help of AI, all of the relevant information can be captured. The customer service industry may also profit from this. Economic Impact and Genesys conducted a poll in 2021 that found that 65% of customer experience executives who used AI technology saw an improvement in agent productivity. Collaboration in the workplace and communication with clients are both improved because of technological advancements. Artificial intelligence allows for easier communication with distant employees.

Considering that more than 4.7 million workers in the United States now work remotely at least some of the time, this is a crucial feature for companies to think about. Those who work from home rely heavily on video calls, but how might AI improve this? Poor video call connections may be a major distraction for workers. However, AI can provide more reliable connections to prevent problems, maintain productive cooperation, and lessen the need for large files. Using AI, we can provide telecommuters with the whole office experience, down to the lights and wallpaper. External partnerships also benefit from enhanced internal collaborations. Personalization is another service that AI may provide to strengthen bonds with clients. Data provides AI with the ability to learn about and cater to a particular user base. With this information, websites and other forms of digital material may be personalized for each user, increasing their interest and loyalty to the brand. So that human agents may focus on more complicated consumer questions, AI chatbots can leverage this customization to meet the demands of each individual client.

2.1 Regional View

The papers to be reviewed under this subject were also taken from online search engines such as Google Scholar and PubMed following the aforementioned rigorous selection and assessment process and adding the required jurisdiction under this subject to be associated with Asian Pacific countries. Papers selected under this review were to be from the Asian Pacific region.

The fast development of AI in recent years has reshaped economies all around the world and the ways in which people earn a living. Despite the many advantages and opportunities presented by AI, its rapid spread throughout Asia has stoked fears of job loss, sometimes known as "AI anxiety." Countries in Asia, including China, Japan,

and South Korea, have made great progress in AI R&D and deployment, making the region a global leader in the field. Artificial intelligence (AI) is being used across a wide range of sectors, from manufacturing and healthcare to banking and customer service, with the goal of increasing production, efficiency, and accuracy. Although this technology has many potential benefits, such as decreased prices and increased competitiveness, it has also caused some people to worry about their jobs in the future.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the practice of programming a computer to do a task in a humanlike manner by making use of novel technical adaptations (Bohr and Memarzadeh 2020). Artificial intelligence not only increases productivity but also aids in the development of successful organizational processes (Tursunbayeva & Renkema 2022). The healthcare industry, in particular, has seen a tremendous surge in the usage of AI in recent years (Bhatia 2021). When considering the breadth and depth of human experience, healthcare stands out as particularly important (Wu et al., 2021). Healthcare is striving to accommodate a growing population while also using AI to improve patient outcomes (Kreutzer & Sirrenberg, 2020). The use of AI has ramifications on the structure of healthcare jobs in several ways (Tursunbayeva & Renkema, 2022). According to Tong et al. (2021), AI allows for the tracking of individual workers' output, which boosts both productivity and efficiency.

Artificial intelligence improves output because workers can more effectively gather, analyze, and use data related to healthcare operations and activities. Additionally, AI may be used by management to assess and distinguish the performance of important competent staff and workers (Zhou et al., 2021). Artificial intelligence (AI) greatly simplifies the archiving of extensive medical data, which in turn helps medical professionals and other healthcare workers carry out their duties and increase their productivity (Tong et al., 2021). AI not only aids in the precise assessment of staff performance, but it also lays out a plan for self-learning skills and suggests adjustments that might boost output (Kreutzer & Sirrenberg, 2020). AI allows businesses to connect employees' strategic objectives with their performance, which in turn motivates them to increase output (Zhao, Cooke & Wang 2021).

In operations management, artificial intelligence (AI) aids and enhances human performance in a number of contexts. AI, for instance, may increase such business metrics as output, quality, customer satisfaction, return on investment, and employee autonomy. Evidence from visual recognition-aided audits was provided by Sun (2019), lending credence to the application of AI in product inspection. It may also be utilized for corporate resource planning, where it can be put to use in assessing customers, gaining insights into how to better manage products and processes, and redistributing personnel to meet fluctuating demands (Wang et al., 2019). Artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms may speed up the analysis of customer input, which in turn provides designers with useful information and managers with aid in positioning the product and creation of products through design elements (Singh & Tucker, 2017).

Customer focus and individualization are propelled by the suggestions made by AI algorithms. As a result, businesses are better able to capitalize on competitive advantages, ultimately leading to happier customers (Grover et al., 2020). Supply chain management, which has been identified as a critical driver of growth, is another important area of application. Artificial intelligence helps supply chain management by facilitating collaboration and information exchange (Gupta et al., 2020). Meeting client demands is the ultimate goal of an effective supply chain (Muggy & Stamm, 2020).

Budgeted expenses, such as those associated with procurement and efficient resource usage, are a common target for the application of such algorithms. Launching new goods in response to consumer demand is yet another significant use case for AI-powered algorithms in the downstream supply chain (Grover et al., 2020). Although many applications of AI have been proposed, it is generally assumed that a mutually beneficial partnership between humans and AI algorithms is essential to the technology's widespread adoption.

Between May 26 and June 9, 2023, researchers at Ipsos Global surveyed 22,816 people across 31 countries who were under the age of 75 (Vahdat, 2022). The survey highlighted both the excitement and the worry that consumers throughout the globe feel about the possible impacts of artificial intelligence. Concerns regarding the potential influence of AI on the workplace were highest in Thailand (69%), Malaysia (62%), Indonesia (62%), and India (51%) (Sharma, 202). Globally, 36% anticipate that AI will replace their present employment, while 57% anticipate that AI will affect the way people operate in their current careers. The proportion of employees anticipating each form of disruption varies greatly by demographic characteristics, with the greatest rates in Southeast Asia and the lowest rates in Northern Europe. People in Singapore believe artificial intelligence would increase their free time and enhance their access to entertainment. However, 41% believe that AI will replace their occupations over the next five years, and 67% believe that AI will transform the way people accomplish their professions (Sithambaram & Tajudeen, 2022). When compared to the rest of the world, this figure is astronomical. This pattern was also seen in Malaysia, where 81 percent of respondents anticipated that AI would affect their productivity at work, and 62 percent believed that AI will eventually replace human workers. When asked whether artificial intelligence (AI) goods and services have significantly altered their lives, respondents from Asia likewise gave the highest ratings possible. South Korea had the highest percentage (73%) in the world, followed by Thailand (72%), Indonesia (72%), and Malaysia (71%) (Sarker et al., 2021).

As AI becomes more common in the workplace, it is essential, from a managerial perspective, to make adjustments to how employees' performance is monitored and evaluated. This is because of the drastic changes COVID-19 has brought to the workplace. Clinical professionals in China have indicated heightened stress after being moved from their home region of Hubei due to these unique conditions (Mo et al., 2020). The former is the first location of coronavirus manifestations. Stress and concern for a lost loved one at work were discovered to go hand in hand by Mo et al. (2020). There was already a lot of pressure on healthcare workers, and the increased usage of AI presented new challenges. Therefore, Mo et al. (2020) believe that in addition to financial remuneration, medical practitioners should be granted non-monetary incentives, including access to a strong professional social support system in order to build psychological resilience (Mo et al., 2020).

As an in-kind remuneration, healthcare workers in China often get free meals. Overtime compensation or extra time off should be provided once the healthcare business in China is less stressed. Each worker should be paid more when the distinctions between work and personal life become blurrier as a result of AI. Despite the unusual nature of the task and the significant danger of exposure, medical professionals should be judged on their performance based on the results they were expected to produce prior to and during the epidemic (Wittbold et al., 2020). One may

also argue that the use of robots powered by artificial intelligence improves workplace morale. Therefore, from a psychological standpoint, lengthy hours spent in direct client contact might lead to fatigue and anxiety about contracting coronavirus. As a result, people become exhausted, frustrated, and less productive. Seventy-one percent of Chinese medical professionals reportedly experienced depression and insomnia as a result of the pandemic (Lai, Ma, & Wang, 2020). Work-related stress may be mitigated, thanks to robots. Using those helps reassure everyone involved while dealing with patients who may be afflicted with coronavirus. Wisskirchen et al. (2017) argue that the emergence of virtual work groups and other types of social isolation may be hindering workers' capacity to work together successfully and creatively. However, should a colleague get sick and they need to take over care of patients, they feel less pressure since they have instantaneous access to their patient's electronic medical records. They may just split up the job remotely and collaborate to complete it. This encourages a work ethic of "work when you want it" and boosts productivity.

2.2. Impact of AI on Employee Performance in the Philippines

The papers to be reviewed under this subject were also taken from online search engines such as Google Scholar and PubMed following the aforementioned rigorous selection and assessment process and adding the required jurisdiction under the specific subject of AI's impact on employee performance and morale in the Philippines. Those that addressed the subject but did not focus on the Philippines were excluded from this review.

According to a research titled *Future Ready Business: Assessing Asia Pacific's Growth Potential Through AI*, the adoption of AI in the Philippines would lead to a 1.7-fold rise in the country's rate of innovation by 2025 and a near doubling of employee productivity improvements (Niehueser & Boak, 2020). Microsoft and International Data Corporation Asia/Pacific conducted research in the Philippines polling 109 company executives and 100 employees. Business executives in the Philippines are almost unanimous in their belief that AI is crucial to their company's ability to compete, yet only around half of Philippine businesses have begun to use AI. Businesses that have already started using AI anticipate a 1.5 times competitive advantage by the year 2025 (Odugbesan et al., 2023).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the defining technology of our time because it speeds up company transformation, paves the way for innovation, increases staff productivity, and guarantees continued development. Economies and companies who have yet to start their AI journey risk falling behind global leaders who are already reaping the advantages. Olan et al. (2022) examined six factors—data, strategy, investments, culture, competencies, and infrastructure—that are essential to a country's AI journey's success. It revealed that for the Philippines to advance more rapidly in the field of artificial intelligence, it must prioritize strengthening all sectors, notably its investments and data (Olan et al., 2022). The Philippines is not yet prepared to use AI. There is a serious need for the Philippines to increase its level of preparedness. To ensure their company's long-term success, CEOs should prioritize AI development and make consistent investments in this game-changing technology.

The three biggest challenges faced by business leaders who are adopting AI are a lack of thought leadership and leadership commitment to invest in AI; a lack of skills,

resources, and continuous learning programs; and a lack of advanced analytics or adequate infrastructure and tools to develop actionable insights (Oosthuizen, 2019). The study's findings showed that organizations with a strong corporate culture were more likely to succeed in their artificial intelligence endeavors. According to a survey of business leaders and workers (Nguyen & Malik, 2022), cultural traits that encourage AI journeys, such as risk-taking, proactive innovation, and cross-function collaboration across teams, are not yet widespread. Filipino workers are less convinced than their country's top executives that their firms are culturally equipped.

According to research conducted by Malik et al. (2021), company owners and employees in the Philippines have optimistic views on the future of work as it relates to artificial intelligence. The vast majority of people think that artificial intelligence would improve their current occupations or at least make them less monotonous (Malik et al., 2021). Business executives are split on whether AI will displace employment or create them; seventeen percent are optimistic. Workers, on the other hand, are more hopeful, with only five percent predicting that AI will replace jobs and fifteen percent predicting that it will generate new ones. However, after three years, only six percent of employees anticipate any effect on their employment. Workers are more open to acquiring new skills than their managers give them credit for, according to the survey. While just four percent of employees are uninterested in learning new skills, sixteen percent of managers and owners feel that way.

Chua et al. (2023) and Kshetri (2021), agents' productivity at Philippine call centers rose by 13.8 percent on average, as assessed by the number of client problems resolved per hour thanks to OpenAI's GPT, the massive language model on which ChatGPT is constructed. Researchers at Stanford University's Digital Economy Lab and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology's Sloan School of Management found that the productivity of 5,179 agents at a Fortune 500 software company that specializes in business process software increased by 13.8% across three metrics: the average time it took to resolve a chat decreased, the average number of chats resolved per hour increased, and the average percentage of resolved chats was higher (Chua et al., 2023). Agents with lower levels of training and experience saw a greater increase in production, whereas those with higher levels of training and experience saw a smaller increase in productivity. Agents were also ranked according to the research team's average call efficiency, resolution rate, and customer satisfaction survey results from the quarter before the AI system was implemented. The lowest-performing group increased their output by thirty-five percent. According to the study's findings, agents who had just been using the AI assistant for two months were equally as productive as those who had been using it for six months. It was expected that highly talented people would gain less from AI recommendations since doing so would expose the person's tacit knowledge (Chua et al., 2023). What this means is that the AI was trained using data from more experienced and knowledgeable staff members; thus, their recommendations reflect their knowledge and wisdom (Rosales et al., 2020). What they found was evidence that, with AI support, low-skill agents may learn to communicate more like high-skill agents, which might help keep employees from leaving the sector. The study's authors concluded that an AI system could facilitate knowledge sharing among employees more effectively than a busy manager because the system could capture tacit information that was previously impossible for managers to express and could make more real-time suggestions than a manager. They also discovered that since the AI helper made it easier for agents to pick

up new skills, customers had a more positive outlook on them. The findings suggest that generative AI working in tandem with humans may have a significant positive influence on the productivity and retention of individual workers, as indicated by the authors (Kshetri, 2021).

3. Conclusion

The main goal of this review is to analyze the impact of AI on employees' work performance and morale in the Philippines. This literature review is divided into three parts: the world, regional, and Philippines views of the impact of AI on employees' work performance and morale in the Philippines. The rise of AI in the 20th and the 21st century has sparked much research that have sought to address AI impact on various industries and on human beings and their productivity. Many researchers have focused on the impact of AI on organization performance, forgetting employee performance and morale, which are critical aspects that need to be addressed. The review began by providing an in-depth analysis of the scholarly works that address the impact of AI on employee performance and morale; then it analyzed scholarly literature that takes a regional view of the research topic and finally focused on the scholarly literature that focuses on the impact of AI on employee performance and morale in the Philippines, which is the country of focus in this research paper. Curiously, there is a dearth of research on how AI influences productivity and morale in the workplace in the Philippines. The effects of AI on the workplace are increasingly being studied, but little is known about how AI will affect Filipino workers at the moment.

The current literature tackling the impact of AI on employee performance and morale has been proven to be a critical endeavor after the review of the available studies, especially those that were conducted in the Philippines. Several studies encourage the progression of the current research to further analyze the impact of AI on Industry 4.0 and employee performance (Gupta et al., 2020, Niehueser & Boak, 2020, Kshetri, 2021, Malik, Budhwar & Kazmi, 2022, Grover, Kar & Dwivedi, 2022, Odugbesan et al., 2023), covering different industries and countries such as the Philippines (Rosales et al., 2020, Bhatia 2021, Fossen & Sorgner, 2021, Bohr & Memarzadeh, 2020, Chua et al., 2023). The gaps identified encompass a lack of research on AI-driven marketing capabilities, insufficient data on AI adoption, specifically in the Philippines, as well as limited insights into the impact of AI on employee management and performance. Additionally, a more comprehensive examination is necessary to explore the consequences of digitalization on work and employee performance, as well as the effect of technology on a company's environmental and social footprint. Notably, more research is needed to explore the application of AI across diverse domains. These identified gaps underscore the urgency for rigorous and comprehensive research regarding AI's impact to better understand the potential benefits and challenges of AI and enable the development of effective strategies for harnessing its power in these areas. Future studies should aim to address the identified gaps to strengthen our comprehension of AI's impact, while also guiding the formulation of effective policies and practices for leveraging AI across various domains. By attending to these gaps, we can formulate effective strategies for AI implementation in different fields and maximize its benefits while minimizing associated risks.

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